

Grain quality

Effect of temperature regime on grain chalkiness in rice

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Grain quality determines the market price of rice. High-yielding varieties with low grain quality are not well accepted by farmers and consumers.

Chalkiness is an important grain quality characteristic because it causes broken grains and nonuniformity of the physical appearance of grains. Chalkiness varies even in the same variety and location. It may be possible that the factors affecting the accumulation of photosynthate during spikelet filling also affect the compactness of starch granules, causing chalkiness.

Temperature affects almost all processes in plants, and chalkiness is probably

not an exception. We studied the effect of temperature regime on chalkiness in rice grains.

Seeds of three cultivars (LMN111, PG56, and HTA60) were sown in Aug 1992 in pots with puddled Maahas clay soil mixed with 3 g of ammonium sulfate. Three seeds were sown per pot but only one plant per pot was left to grow. One month after emergence, the plants were subjected to a 10-h photoperiod to induce flowering. At flowering, they were placed in temperature-controlled growth chambers, with natural light and 80% relative humidity until maturity. The day/night temperature regimes used were: 22/15, 25/15, 30/20, and 35/20 °C. After harvest, rice grains were dehulled and scored for chalkiness using the procedure of the Rice Grain Quality Laboratory, Rice Research Institute, Thailand: 0 = no chalkiness, 1 = less than 10% chalky area, 2 = 10-20%, 3 = 20-50%, 4 = 50-75%, and 5 = above 75%.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

The high temperature regime (35/20 °C) had the most adverse effect on percentage of filled spikelets in all cultivars tested. At low temperatures (22/15 °C), HTA60 was the least sensitive while LMN111 and PG56 had comparable high sensitivity. The 30/20 °C temperature regime resulted in a higher percentage of filled spikelets for the three cultivars tested; HTA60 was the least sensitive to temperature regime (Fig. 1).

Optimum temperatures for low chalkiness were 25/15 °C and 30/20 °C (Fig. 2). Low temperature (22/15 °C) increased chalkiness but not as serious as did high temperature (35/20 °C), although low temperature affected panicle exertion and percentage of fertile spikelets. Despite low number of spikelets to fill, high temperature resulted in poor spikelet filling, although leaves were still green.

Temperature affected chalkiness. Under field conditions, temperature cannot be controlled, so the best way to reduce chalkiness is to select cultivars that are less sensitive to temperature, such as PG56. ■

Scented rice in Jiangxi Province, China

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Gan-xian-da-he-zi, Gi-shui-xiang-nu, Gi-an-xiang-he-zi, and Long-nan-xiang-he are traditional local scented rice cultivars in Jiangxi Province. All three of these are unsuitable for cultivation because of their tall stature, low yield potential, and poor grain appearance, which does not meet the demands of the modern rice market.

We started to work on breeding new scented rices in 1985. Many aromatic rices, including IR841, Basmati 370, and Khao Dawk Mali 105, were selected for use in the crossing program. We followed the objective of breeding semidwarf, high quality rice with slender grain and at least 5% higher yield than

1. Percentage of filled spikelets of HTA60, LMN111, and PG56 at different temperature regimes.

2. Chalkiness score of deepwater rice (HTA60) and floating rices (LMN111 and PG56) subjected to various temperature regimes in growth chambers. IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines. Oct 1993-Jan 1994.